

Agenda, Session 1

Introductions - 15min

Presentation w Discussion - 60min

Break - 5min

Small Group Activity (breakout room) -
20min

Wrap up - 10min

Self-Introductions

Name & where you're from

Professional Interests (including course(s) you're teaching)

One positive & one negative thing about teaching/students

If you had taken a different path....

And anything else you want to share

Nina Kang

Nina Kang, Ed.D. is a Master Lecturer and Assessment Coordinator at the American Language Institute, University of Southern California with 20+ years of teaching experience. She has enjoyed teaching across the world in Bulgaria, China, Korea, Serbia & Montenegro, Uganda, and Uzbekistan and hopes to continue her work in teacher training in the field of English language teaching.

She has presented at numerous international conferences and has been involved in teacher training and curriculum development as a U.S. Department of State English Language Specialist in Hanoi, Vietnam. Her areas of interest include testing assessment specific to writing, collaborative writing models, academic help-seeking skills of international students, technology-enhanced teaching and learning, and online/hybrid content delivery.

**Multi-Mode Feedback in Large
Writing Classrooms at Antonine
University (Beirut, Lebanon)
Presented by Nina Kang**

Multi-Mode Feedback in Writing Classrooms

<p>April 22, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Foundations of Assessment in Language Teaching / Principles of Metacognition</p>
<p>April 29, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Whole Class Feedback: Identifying Common Mistakes with a Focus on Grammar & Mechanics</p>
<p>May 6, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Peer Feedback: Targeted Tasks & Discussions</p>
<p>May 13, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Self Feedback: Showcasing Growth through Writing Portfolios & Projects</p>
<p>May 20, 2022 6:00 – 8:00 p.m. (Beirut) via Zoom</p>	<p>Final Debriefing: Discussing Challenges & Best Practices</p>

Multi-Mode Feedback in Large Writing Classrooms

Workshop Objectives:

- Learn to identify student texts appropriate for modeling feedback on content, stylistic, and grammatical issues
- Introduce and practice using multimodal feedback strategies
- Develop strategies aimed at helping students to construct their own criteria leading to self-corrections and other self-directed skills

Part 1: A New Approach to Assessment

Questions to Consider

1. When and how often should I assess my students?
2. What aspect of language ability should I assess?
3. What kinds of assessment tasks should I use?
4. How do I ensure consistency and meaningful feedback?

1. When and how often should I assess my students?

- Weekly
- Monthly
- Beginning/End
- Continuously
- Every vs Selected Assignments

2. What aspect of language ability should I assess?

- Pronunciation
- Fluency
- Vocabulary
- Grammar
- Content knowledge

2b. More specifically in writing, what aspect of language ability should I assess?

- Content (development of ideas)
- Logical Flow / Organization
- Vocabulary & Register
- Grammar
- Mechanics and Conventions

3. What types of assessment tasks should I use?

- Multiple choice
- True or False
- Cloze (fill-in-the-blanks)
- Essays
- Presentations

4. How do I ensure consistency and meaningful feedback?

- Rubrics
- Standards/Benchmarks

DISUSSION OF STUDENT SAMPLE (B1.2), 339 words

In Lebanon everything is different, so what can be better to university students in Lebanon ,online or on campus learning ? There is a big debate about this topic especially in Lebanon because of the country's situation and its impact on education. On campus learning is better for many reasons.

There are many reasons that gives preference to on campus learning over online learning in Lebanon for university students, one of them is that on campus, everyone can attend classes because it doesn't require internet unlike online learning where internet at home is essential. According to studies, 55% of Lebanese families after the crises are under the poverty level, so students have to work and miss classes to pay university and internet bills,without mentioning electricity crises .

Furthermore, on campus students can interact more with people , they can ask questions and get answered immediately so they can understand more , they also can have friends and build relationships , wich is so important to preserve a good mental health despite all the crises in Lebanon , while in online sessions, students are sitting hours in front of screens , they cant talk with anybody , and if they didn't understand they just leave the meeting.

There is one reason that makes online learning better than on campus learning, is the price of petrol in Lebanon. Recently , petrol tank in Lebanon costs 500 000 L.L , so students who lives far from the university will face a real issue especially with the current economic crisis unlike online learning where students can attend classes from their homes . But this can be fixed by taking a dorm in the university so they can reach it by walking.

In conclusion , on campus learning is better than online because everyone can attend sessions,students can build communities,and they can understand more.Even though in Lebanon everything seems like there is not a promising future but students should believe that they are the true revolution and with education they can change everything .

Trends in Assessment

Cultural relevance

Interactive

Formative (low-stakes)

Application of knowledge & skills

Authentic Assessment, Definition

Incorporates real-world problem solving and tasks that involve active application of knowledge and skills (Stiggins, 1987; Wiggins, 1993)

Traditional vs. Authentic Assessments

Traditional 😊

- Answer choices
- Hypothetical scenarios
- Practice of recall
- Teacher-centered

Authentic 😊

- Performance-based
- Problem-solving
- Response to real-life tasks
- Construction of knowledge
- Application of skills

Traditional or
Authentic
Assessment?

Multiple Choice

QUESTIONS

1- A B C D

2- A B C D

3- A B C D

4- A B C D

5- A B C D

6- A B C D

Traditional or
Authentic
Assessment?

Journaling

Traditional or
Authentic
Assessment?

Discussion

Traditional or Authentic Assessment?

Cloze

CLOZE TEST

*For Lawrence United Washington cut father he his
of really slaves very*

George Washington was the first President of the United States. He was also the commander in chief of all American forces during the American Revolutionary War. For his central role in the beginning of the United States, he is often called the father of country. His mother was Mary Ball and his was Augustine Washington. They owned a plantation with in Virginia. George studied at local schools. George's died when he was eleven. Then his brother helped train him. There is a story that cut down his father's cherry tree. When asked, did not lie and said that he did down the tree. The story means he was honest. We do not know if the story happened.

SCORE:
3/14

?

Part 2: Developing Metacognitive Skills via Student Writing

Metacognitive Skills – self-awareness about one's learning

Higher-order thinking

Control over cognitive process
(develop strategies, make
decisions)

Features of Metacognitive Skills Centered Teaching & Learning

Instructors identify student's strengths and weaknesses >>

By the end of the semester: Students can identify their own S&W.

Instructors prioritize learning needs of students >>

By end of the semester: Students prioritize their learning needs.

Instructors choose topics & set goals >>

By end of the semester: Students choose their own topics and set goals.

Motivation

Intrinsic – internal motivation;
autonomy and self-efficacy

Extrinsic – external motivation;
rewards driven; goal-orientation

Motivation

Summative tasks &
feedbacks

vs.

Formative tasks &
feedbacks

Bloom's Taxonomy in Assessment

Aiming for the **TRANSFER OF KNOWLEDGE**, i.e., the ability to evaluate and create

Bloom's Taxonomy

create

Produce new or original work

Design, assemble, construct, conjecture, develop, formulate, author, investigate

evaluate

Justify a stand or decision

appraise, argue, defend, judge, select, support, value, critique, weigh

analyze

Draw connections among ideas

differentiate, organize, relate, compare, contrast, distinguish, examine, experiment, question, test

apply

Use information in new situations

execute, implement, solve, use, demonstrate, interpret, operate, schedule, sketch

understand

Explain ideas or concepts

classify, describe, discuss, explain, identify, locate, recognize, report, select, translate

remember

Recall facts and basic concepts

define, duplicate, list, memorize, repeat, state

Part 3: Constructing Rubrics to Measure Assessments

Rubric, Definition

- Criteria to evaluate student responses (written and/or spoken)
- Often presented in table format for teachers to score or comment

Reliability & Fairness in Assessing Student Work

Sample Rubric

Essential Elements	1	2	3	4	5
Development of Topic & Details	*No thesis, undeveloped or vague thesis, theme or topic *Few or no relevant details	*Inconsistent or basic development of thesis, theme, or topic; limited in depth or clarity *Details lack elaboration; important details omitted; some details inaccurate	*Adequate development of thesis, theme, or topic; *Conclusion is more than a summary *Details are adequate, accurate, relevant; some elaboration	*Consistently & fully developed thesis, theme or topic; *Draws a conclusion *Details are specific, enhance development, and are elaborated upon	*Clearly & fully developed, original, insightful thesis, theme, topic & conclusion *Rich supporting details are fully elaborated upon & enhance development
Information Integration	*No evidence of understanding the subject or content *No connection between subject or content and task	*Inaccurate or basic understanding of subject or content *Few connections to subject or content and task	*Adequate understanding of subject or content *Implied connection between subject or content and task	*Clear understanding of subject or content *Clear connections between subject or content and task	*In-depth analysis of subject or content *Insightful connections between subject or content information and task
Organization & Format	*Lacks focus and organization or unclear focus organizational strategy *Format of paper is not consistent with assignment	*Establish but does not maintain focus *Organizational strategy includes some transitions *The paper has major formatting issues	Maintains a clear and appropriate focus Logical progression of ideas with transitions, some inconsistencies *Some of the paper is formatted correctly with minor inconsistencies	*Clear and appropriate focus; *Logical & controlled organization throughout; *Appropriate transitions; not formulaic *A majority of the paper is formatted correctly	*Clear and appropriate focus *Effective use of appropriate transitions *Writer expresses relationships among ideas; *Careful & subtle organization *Entire paper is formatted correctly
Word Choice, Sentence Variety and Structure	*Poor sentence structure; many fragments and/or run-ons *No sentence variety *Limited vocabulary; or consistently inappropriate for purpose	*Complete sentences; *Rudimentary sentence variety *Appropriate vocabulary	*Deliberate sentence variety *Effective vocabulary	*Sentence variety enhances style & effect *Varied and precise word choice	*Complex sentence variety enhances style & effect *Sophisticated language
Grammar, Usage & Mechanics	*Errors in grammar, usage & mechanics make writing unclear; or distract *Few or no citations	*Errors in grammar, usage & mechanics disproportionate to length & complexity of piece *Pattern of major citation errors	*Some errors in grammar, usage & mechanics *Pattern of minor citation errors	*Few errors in grammar, usage & mechanics *Some citation errors	*Mastery of grammar, usage & mechanics *Few or no citation errors

1. Discussion of a student sample: What are different ways to assess this writing?

In this picture, there was a mother preparing food for her childrens, and she was very happy with her childrens. And the two childrens drinks juice before eating fishes. And, the dad is very happy with his happy family after a long day of work. (A2.2)

Sample

In this picture, there was a mother preparing food for her children, and she was very happy with her chidlrens. And the two chidlrens drinks juice before eating fishes. And, the dad is very happy with his happy family after a long day of work.

- Grammar
- Vocab
- Style

2. Discussion of a student sample: What are different ways to assess this writing?

American sniper is a film genre in which the protagonist are thrust into a series of events that typically include violence, fighting, physical feats, rescues and frantic chases. Action films trend to feature a mostly resourceful hero this what i like it. (B1.1)

References

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